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Infrastructure Score Card As A Tool For Job Creation

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ABSTRACT

Infrastructure score card is the systematic rating of the quality of infrastructure available in any country or society. Whereas, for example, Nigerian and United States of America's infrastructure are currently rated F1 and C - respectively, the gaps in the two countries infrastructure are clearly shown. Nigeria's infrastructure ranking of 1.51 out of 5 points means it's unfit for purpose and constituting danger to public health and safety. While ensuring the smooth running of any society, Infrastructure is a key criterion in determining a country's Global Competitiveness Index (GCI). Nigeria's 2022 ranking of 143 out of 195 countries in infrastructure quality with an investment of 3% of her GDP amounting to a mere \$664 per capita per annum compares little with developed countries averaging 5% of their GDP or \$3060 per capita per annum. This translates to quantum deficit of infrastructure in Nigeria and an insight to the required engineering projects and potential jobs available. The authors therefore recommended that, to improve the quality of life in Nigeria and strengthen competitiveness, a strategic and holistic plan to review, modernize, and invest in infrastructure are very imperative. Basic maintenance should be a priority so that legacy systems can be improved upon. Policy makers and government must understand that a nation's infrastructure is indeed as strong as its weakest link, just as in all other economic indices.

Keyword: infrastructure, scorecard, systematic, rating, quality, job creation, infrastructure deficit, global competitiveness index.

INTRODUCTION

The word infrastructure is a combination of the Latin prefix "infra", meaning "below" and "structure" Hornby (2000) defines infrastructure as the basic systems and services that are necessary for country or an organization, for example buildings, transport, water and power supplies and administrative systems. Infrastructure can be defined as the basic physical and organizational structures needed for the operation of a society or enterprise, or the services and facilities necessary for an economy to function. The term can also refer to the technical structures that support a society, such as roads, water supply. sewers, power grids, telecommunications, and so forth (Kumar, 2005).

Ali (2023) from Statista (2023) states that the cornerstone of any modern society is a well-functioning infrastructure. Infrastructure therefore is the bedrock on which any economy is built. Infrastructure facilitates business transactions, transitions and increases a country's standard of living plus overall efficiency.

There is a direct proportionality between country's infrastructure quality and her Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Infrastructure is a vital necessity for economic growth while economic growth creates room for more investment in infrastructure. It is therefore very imperative to show the line between sustainable infrastructure development and job creation / economic growth plus Human Development Index. The Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations of 2015 – 2030 (15 years) has 17 goals and goal number 9 (Industries, Innovation and Infrastructure) seeks to build resilient Infrastructure, promote sustainable industrialization and foster innovation.

The reason for Nigeria's low GDP per capita, otherwise known as Purchasing Power parity (PPP) can therefore easily be linked to her weak infrastructure base. In order to eliminate the disparity in the purchasing power, it is important to strengthen our infrastructure base as infrastructure developments stimulate economic growth by increase access to markets, improving transportation, and enhance trade. It is on this basis that this study is carried out to evaluate the infrastructure scorecard in order to create job in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Nigeria faces significant infrastructure challenges, including inadequate transportation networks, unreliable energy supply, and insufficient water and sanitation facilities. These infrastructure gaps hinder economic growth, limit job creation, and affect the overall quality of life. Despite efforts to address these challenges, the infrastructure deficit remains a major obstacle to Nigeria's development. For instance, the unreliable energy supply, characterized by frequent power outages and inadequate generation capacity, affects industrial productivity, increases costs, and limits economic growth. Furthermore, insufficient

water and sanitation facilities pose serious health risks, reduce the quality of life, and increase the burden on the healthcare system. Therefore, there is a need for a comprehensive approach to assess and improve infrastructure development, which can, in turn, stimulate job creation and economic growth.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to explore the infrastructure scorecard in stimulating job creation. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine the significance of infrastructure in supporting economic growth and development.
2. Examine the role of infrastructure score card in a Nation's GDP and some key areas for evaluating the infrastructure score card.
3. To investigate the relationship between sustainable infrastructure and SDGs.
4. To explore the key components of global competitiveness index
5. Evaluate the relationship between infrastructure scorecard determination and job creation.
6. Access the impact of infrastructure score card on the economy.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the significance of infrastructure in supporting economic growth and development?
2. What is the role of infrastructure score card in a Nation's GDP and what are the key areas for evaluating the infrastructure score card?
3. What is the relationship between sustainable infrastructure and SDGs?
4. What are the key components of global competitiveness index?
5. How does infrastructure scorecard determination lead to job creation?
6. How does infrastructure score card impact on the economy?

Significance of the Study

This study aims to explore the potential of an infrastructure scorecard as a tool for job creation in Nigeria. The findings of this study will contribute to the development of effective strategies for infrastructure development and job creation. The study's significance lies in its potential to:

1. Identify infrastructure gaps: The study will identify the infrastructure gaps that need to be addressed to stimulate job creation.
2. Inform policy decisions: The study's findings will inform policy decisions on infrastructure development and job creation.
3. Promote sustainable development: The study will explore the potential of infrastructure development to promote sustainable development and job creation.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

Scope

The study focuses on:

1. Significance of infrastructure in supporting economic growth and development.
2. The role of infrastructure score card in a Nation's GDP and some key areas for evaluating the infrastructure score card.
3. The relationship between sustainable infrastructure and SDGs.
4. The key components of global competitiveness index
5. The relationship between infrastructure scorecard determination and job creation.
6. The impact of infrastructure score card on the economy.

This study has some limitations, including:

1. Scope: The study focuses on infrastructure development and job creation in Nigeria, which may limit its generalizability to other contexts.
2. Data availability: The study's findings depend on the availability and quality of data on infrastructure development and job creation in Nigeria.
3. Methodological limitations: The study uses a specific methodology to develop an infrastructure scorecard, which may have its own limitations and biases.

Literature Review

Conceptual Framework

Infrastructure can be defined as the basic physical and organizational structures needed for the operation of a society or enterprise, or the services and facilities necessary for an economy to function. Hornby (2000) defines infrastructure as the basic systems and services that are necessary for country or an organization, for example buildings, transport, water and power supplies and administrative systems. While an infrastructure scorecard can be seen as a valuable tool for identifying a nation's infrastructure deficit and promoting economic growth and development.

Significance of Infrastructure in Supporting Economic Growth and Development

In Nigeria, infrastructure development has been identified as a key driver of economic growth. A study examining the impact of government infrastructural development on transportation, road, water, and telecommunication found that infrastructure development on transport services was positive and significant in explaining changes in real GDP (Agbigbe, 2018). However, the study also noted that infrastructure development on road, water, and telecommunications were negative and not significant in explaining changes in Nigeria's real GDP within the study period.

Key Areas of Infrastructure Development:

1. **Transportation:** Efficient transportation systems reduce logistics costs, improve market accessibility, and increase trade opportunities, enhancing economic growth and regional development (World Bank, 2019).
2. **Road Infrastructure:** Quality road infrastructure increases GDP per capita and reduces ship turnaround time, making it an essential component of Nigeria's economic growth (Ogunjumo, 2018).
3. **Telecommunication:** Well-developed telecommunications infrastructure enables seamless communication and data exchange, fostering innovation, entrepreneurship, and global collaboration (ITU, 2020).

The significance of infrastructure development in Nigeria can be seen in several areas:

1. **Job Creation and Poverty Reduction:** Infrastructure development contributes to job creation and poverty reduction by generating employment opportunities during construction and long-term maintenance (World Bank, 2019).
2. **Regional Development and Global Competitiveness:** Infrastructure development promotes regional development and global competitiveness by improving connectivity to rural and remote areas (AfDB, 2018).
3. **Sustainable and Resilient Infrastructure:** Building resilient infrastructure that can withstand natural disasters and shocks is essential for long-term economic stability (IPCC, 2018).

To achieve sustainable economic growth and development, Nigeria needs to prioritize infrastructure development, focusing on building transformative infrastructure that provides lasting social and economic value for everyone. This can be achieved through:

1. **Increased Investment:** Investing in infrastructure development can have significant economic benefits, including increased productivity, job creation, and economic growth (Calderón & Servén, 2004).
2. **Public-Private Partnerships:** Leveraging public-private partnerships can help mobilize funds for infrastructure development and improve the efficiency of infrastructure projects (World Bank, 2019).
3. **Proper Planning and Project Management:** Ensuring proper planning, project management and reduced corruption is crucial for successful infrastructure development (Transparency International, 2020).

Infrastructure Score Card

An infrastructure scorecard is a valuable tool for identifying a nation's infrastructure deficit and promoting economic growth and development. The most recent infrastructure report in Nigeria is the one conducted in 2017 by the Nigeria Society of Engineers (NSE). NSE (2017), referring to a study by the

World Economic Forum in collaboration with the Boston Consulting Group noted that a country’s competitive economic advantage clearly depends on a properly articulated infrastructure vision and long term planning. Since infrastructure planning, design, development and maintenance is the core of civil engineers professional practice, it is therefore very vital that we monitor the state of the county’s infrastructure to among other things show the level of available jobs and strategies towards them. NSE (2017) stated thus “the overall rating of the Nigeria’s infrastructure stock was F1 with a score of 1.51 out of 5. This is unfit for purpose and therefore constitutes danger to public safety.” Infrastructure in Nigeria therefore degraded from 2.08 (E2) in 2015 to 1.51 (F1) in 2017.

There are some key areas for evaluating the infrastructure score card:

1. Road Infrastructure: Assessing the condition, quality, and accessibility of roads is crucial. According to the Federal Ministry of Works and Housing, Nigeria's road network is vast, but only 30% of its estimated 200,000 kilometers are paved, contributing to poor road conditions (FMWH, 2020).
2. Energy Infrastructure: Evaluating power generation, transmission, and distribution is essential. Nigeria's power generation capacity is insufficient to meet demand, hindering economic growth (Energy Commission of Nigeria, 2020).
3. Digital Infrastructure: Assessing internet penetration, mobile coverage, and digital literacy rates is vital. Nigeria's digital infrastructure is underdeveloped, with low internet penetration and digital literacy rates (Nigerian Communications Commission, 2020).
4. Transportation Infrastructure: Evaluating railways, airports, and seaports is necessary. Nigeria's transportation infrastructure requires improvement to facilitate economic growth (Nigerian Railway Corporation, 2020).

Figure 1 below is the overall infrastructure rating (2015 and 2017)

Figure 2 depicts

F	F3	1.88	Unfit for purpose	Infrastructure has failed or is on the verge of failure, exposing the public to health and safety hazards. Immediate attention is required
	F2	1.34		
	F1	1.67		
E	E3	1.68	Poor State	Infrastructure is on the verge of failure and urgent rehabilitation is required to prevent complete failure or restore to serviceable state
	E2	2.01		
	E1	2.34		
D	D3	2.35	At Risk	Infrastructure is not coping with demand and is poorly maintained. It is likely that the public will be subjected to severe inconvenience and even danger without prompt attention
	D2	2.68		
	D1	3.00		
C	C3	3.01	Satisfactory for now	Infrastructure condition is acceptable although stressed at peak periods. It will need investment in the current medium term expenditure framework period to avoid serious deficiencies
	C2	3.19		
	C1	3.36		
B	B3	3.37	Comparable to Africa's Best	Infrastructure is in good condition and properly maintained. It satisfies current demands and is sufficiently robust to deal with minor incidents
	B2	3.86		
	B1	4.04		
A	A3	4.35	Comparable to global best	Infrastructure is comparable to the best internationally in every respect. It is in excellent condition and well maintained, with capacity to endure pressure from unusual events
	A2	4.68		
	A1	5.00		

INFRASTRUCTURE SCORE IN 2015 AND 2017

Table 1 – Nigerian Infrastructure Score in 2015 and 2017

	2015	2017	Rating Parameters
Oil & Gas	E2 (2.04)	E3 (1.98)	
ICT -		E3 (1.79)	Internet broadband, cloud computing, telecommunications, radio, Tv, artificial intelligence and robotics infrastructure
Transportation	E3 (2.32)	F1(1.64)	
Healthcare	E3 (2.30)	F1(1.60)	
Security and Law Enforcement	E1(1.64)	F3(1.24)	
Education	E3(2.14)	F2 (1.44)	Primary Schools, Secondary Schools, Vocational Institutions/Technical Colleges and Tertiary Institutions (Univ. & Polytechnics)
Electric Power	E3(2.16)	F2(1.36)	
Tourism	E3(2.11)	F2(1.43)	
Agriculture	-	F1(1.55)	Food grain storage facilities, food processing facilities and irrigation infrastructure
Technology transfer in the science and technology		- Very low	
Water, Sanitation & Hygiene (WASH)	E2(1.99)	F2 (1.29)	
Emergency Response Infrastructure	E3 (1.79)	F3(1.25)	

Source: NSE (2017)

2019 Global Country Ranking by Infrastructure Quality

Nigeria does not feature in the 100 best considering the quality of infrastructure. Singapore leads the pack with a value of 95.4 over 100 followed by Netherlands and Hong Kong SAR with scores of 94.3 and 94 respectively. Egypt, Morocco and South Africa, are the only African countries that made the list with

73.1, 72.6 and 68.6 and 82nd, 83rd and 99th positions respectively (Statista, 2019). Calculation of the Unifrastructure score are based on:

- ✓ Road connectivity index
- ✓ Quality of roads
- ✓ Railroad density
- ✓ Efficiency of train services
- ✓ Airport connectivity
- ✓ Efficiency of air transport services
- ✓ Linear shipping connectivity index
- ✓ Efficiency of seaport services
- ✓ Electrification rate
- ✓ Electric power transmission and distribution losses
- ✓ Exposure to unsafe drinking water
- ✓ Reliability of water supply.

Table 2 below shows 2019 top 100 countries ranking by quality of infrastructure

Source: Statista (2019)

Infrastructure Sustainability

Infrastructure sustainability is a critical aspect of modern development, ensuring that infrastructure systems are designed, constructed, and operated to meet the needs of present and future generations. Infrastructure sustainability is intricately linked with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 9, which focuses on building resilient infrastructure, promoting inclusive and sustainable industrialization, and fostering innovation. According to the United Nations (2020), the SDGs provide a framework for achieving sustainable development, and infrastructure sustainability is critical to achieving these goals.

Key Aspects of Infrastructure Sustainability:

1. **Environmental Sustainability:** Infrastructure development should minimize environmental impacts, such as greenhouse gas emissions and pollution, to ensure sustainable development (IPCC, 2014).
2. **Economic Sustainability:** Infrastructure investments should be economically viable, providing benefits that outweigh costs and ensuring long-term financial sustainability (World Bank, 2019).
3. **Social Sustainability:** Infrastructure development should prioritize social equity, accessibility, and community engagement, ensuring that benefits are shared fairly among stakeholders (UN-Habitat, 2020).
4. **Resilience and Adaptability:** Infrastructure systems should be designed to withstand natural disasters, climate change, and other disruptions, with the ability to adapt to changing conditions (ASCE, 2020).

Sustainable Development Goals

Infrastructure sustainability aligned with the SDGs in following areas:

1. **Goal 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure:** Develop quality, reliable, sustainable, and resilient infrastructure to support economic development and human well-being (United Nations, 2020). Economies with a diversified industrial sector and strong infrastructure sustained less damage from the Covid pandemic while mono economies with weak infrastructure have prolonged impact of the pandemic, UN (2023). The deficit of sustainable infrastructure base in Nigeria has very adversely ensured very slow recovery from the pandemics.
2. **Goal 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities:** Ensure that cities and human settlements are inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable (United Nations, 2020).
3. **Goal 13: Climate Action:** Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts by developing climate-resilient infrastructure (IPCC, 2014).

The 17 SDG's are shown in Figure 3 above. All signatory countries are expected to achieve the stated goals not later than 2030

Sustainable Infrastructure Investment

United Nations Environment Programme opined that “sustainable infrastructure systems are those that are planned, designed, constructed, operated and decommissioned in a manner that ensures economic and financial, social, environmental (including climate resilience), and institutional sustainability over the entire infrastructure life cycle. Sustainable Infrastructure can include built infrastructure, natural infrastructure or hybrid infrastructure that contains elements of both”.

Achieving SDG's by 2030 with net zero emissions by 2050 requires massive investment in sustainable and resilient infrastructure. Till year 2050, USD 6.9 trillion is estimated to be spent annually to meet development goals and create low carbon, climate resilient future.

Global Competitiveness

The Global Competitiveness Index (GCI) is a comprehensive measure developed by the World Economic Forum (WEF) to evaluate a country's ability to provide prosperity to its citizens. It assesses various factors that drive economic growth, productivity, and competitiveness across nations.

Key Components of the GCI:

1. Institutions: Evaluating the quality of public and private institutions, including governance, judicial independence, and property rights (World Economic Forum, 2020).
2. Infrastructure: Assessing the state of physical infrastructure, such as roads, bridges, and transportation systems (World Economic Forum, 2020).
3. Macroeconomic Environment: Examining the stability of the macroeconomic framework, including inflation, fiscal policy, and debt management (World Economic Forum, 2020).
4. Health and Primary Education: Evaluating the quality of healthcare and primary education systems (World Health Organization, 2019).
5. Higher Education and Training: Assessing the availability and quality of higher education and vocational training (UNESCO, 2020).
6. Goods Market Efficiency: Examining the efficiency of goods markets, including competition, market size, and trade policies (World Bank, 2020).

7. Labor Market Efficiency: Evaluating the flexibility and efficiency of labor markets, including labor laws, wage flexibility, and talent utilization (International Labor Organization, 2020).
8. Financial Market Development: Assessing the development and stability of financial markets, including access to credit and financial services (World Bank, 2020).
9. Technological Readiness: Evaluating a country's ability to adopt and utilize new technologies (World Economic Forum, 2020).
10. Market Size: Assessing the size of a country's domestic and international market (World Trade Organization, 2020).
11. Business Sophistication: Evaluating the quality of business processes, innovation, and entrepreneurship (World Economic Forum, 2020).
12. Innovation: Assessing a country's capacity for innovation, including research and development, intellectual property protection, and entrepreneurship (World Intellectual Property Organization, 2020).

METHODOLOGY:

The GCI is calculated based on over 110 variables, with two-thirds coming from the Executive Opinion Survey and one-third from publicly available sources (World Economic Forum, 2020). The index separates countries into three stages of development:

- i. Factor-driven stage: Countries compete based on factor endowments, such as natural resources and unskilled labor (World Economic Forum, 2020).
- ii. Efficiency-driven stage: Countries compete based on efficient production processes and product quality (World Economic Forum, 2020).
- iii. Innovation-driven stage: Countries compete based on innovation, entrepreneurship, and the creation of new products and services (World Economic Forum, 2020).

Criticisms and Limitations:

Some critics argue that the GCI prioritizes economic growth over social and environmental considerations (Krugman, 1994). Additionally, the report's methodology has been questioned, with concerns about the weighting of different pillars and the potential for bias in the Executive Opinion Survey (Høyland et al., 2012).

The 2022 GCI of countries are shown in table 3 below.

Table 3 – GCI of Countries (2018 – 2022)

Country 2021	2018 2022	2019	2020		
Australia	19	18	18	22	19
Austria	18	19	16	22	20
Bahrain	-	-	-	-	30
Belgium	26	27	25	24	21
Botswana	-	-	-	61	58
Brazil	60	59	56	57	59
Bulgaria	48	48	48	53	53
Canada	10	13	8	8	14
Chile	35	42	38	44	45
China	13	14	20	16	17
Colombia	58	52	54	56	57
Croatia	61	60	60	59	46
Cyprus	41	41	30	33	40
Czech Republic	29	33	33	34	26
Denmark	6	8	2	3	1

Estonia	31	35	28	28	22
Finland	16	15	13	11	8
France	28	31	32	29	28
Germany	15	17	17	15	15
Greece	57	58	49	46	47
Hong	2	2	5	7	5
Hungary	47	47	47	42	39
Iceland	24	20	21	21	16
India	44	43	43	43	37
Indonesia	43	32	40	37	44
Ireland	12	7	12	13	11
Israel	21	24	26	27	25
Italy	42	44	44	41	41
Japan	25	30	34	31	34
Jordan	52	57	58	49	56
Kazakhstan	38	34	42	35	43
Korea Rep.	27	28	23	23	27
Latvia	40	40	41	38	35
Lithuania	32	29	31	30	29
Luxembourg	11	12	15	12	13
Malaysia	22	22	27	25	52
Mexico	51	50	53	55	55
Mexico	51	50	53	55	55
Netherlands	4	6	4	4	6
New Zealand	23	21	22	20	31
Norway	8	11	7	6	9
Peru	54	55	52	58	54
Philippines	50	46	45	52	48
Poland	34	38	39	47	50
Portugal	33	39	37	36	42
Qatar	14	10	14	17	18
Romania	49	49	51	48	51
Saudi Arabia	39	26	24	32	24
Singapore	3	1	1	5	3
Slovak Republic	55	53	57	50	49
Slovenia	37	37	35	40	38
South Africa	53	56	59	62	60
Spain	36	36	36	39	36
Sweden	9	9	6	2	4
Switzerland	5	4	3	1	2
Taiwan, China	17	16	11	8	7
Thailand	30	25	29	28	33
Turkey	46	51	46	51	52
UAE	7 5 9 9 12	5	9	9	12
United Kingdom	20	23	19	18	23
USA 1 3 10 10 10	1	3	10	10	10

Source: 2022 World Competitiveness Ranking (imd.org)

NIGERIA’S GLOBAL COMPETITIVE INDEX (2015 – 2019)

Table 4 below shows Nigeria’s GCI from 2015 to 2019

DATE	VALUE	RANK	NO OF COUNTRIES
2015		127	144
2016		127	
2017	48.04	125	137
2018	47.53	115	140
2019	48.33	116	140

Job Creation through Infrastructure Score Card

Infrastructure development is crucial for job creation in Nigeria, and a well-structured infrastructure scorecard can help track progress, identify areas for improvement, and inform investment decisions. Infrastructure contributes to job creation in the following ways:

1. **Transportation Infrastructure:** Investments in roads, rail lines, and public transportation systems create jobs in construction, civil engineering, and transportation services. According to the World Bank, every \$1 invested in infrastructure can generate up to 3 jobs in the short term and up to 6 jobs in the long term (World Bank, 2019).
2. **Energy Infrastructure:** Renewable energy projects, such as solar and wind power, can create new job opportunities in installation, maintenance, and manufacturing. The International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) estimates that the renewable energy sector could support up to 24 million jobs globally by 2030 (IRENA, 2019).
3. **Digital Infrastructure:** Investments in digital connectivity and ICT infrastructure can enable remote work, e-commerce, and digital entrepreneurship, creating jobs in the tech sector. A report by the Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC) highlights the importance of digital infrastructure in driving economic growth and job creation in Nigeria (NCC, 2020).

Key Sectors Benefiting from Infrastructure Development:

1. **Construction:** Civil engineers, surveyors, laborers, and materials suppliers benefit from infrastructure development projects, such as road construction and building of public facilities. According to the Nigerian Society of Engineers, infrastructure development is critical for driving economic growth and job creation in Nigeria (NSE, 2020).
2. **Renewable Energy:** Solar panel technicians, installers, and battery production jobs are created through investments in renewable energy infrastructure. The Solar Power Naija initiative aims to create 250,000 new energy jobs by 2030.
3. **ICT and Digital Economy:** Software development, digital marketing, and e-commerce operations benefit from investments in digital infrastructure. A report by the World Economic Forum highlights the importance of digital skills in driving economic growth and job creation (WEF, 2020).
4. **Transportation and Logistics:** Drivers, logistics coordinators, and transportation managers benefit from investments in transportation infrastructure. According to the Federal Ministry of Transportation, investments in transportation infrastructure can improve efficiency and reduce costs, leading to increased economic activity and job creation (FMoT, 2020).

Benefits of Infrastructure Scorecard:

- a. **Improved Planning:** Helps identify areas for improvement and inform investment decisions.
- b. **Job Creation:** Tracks progress in infrastructure development and its impact on job creation.
- c. **Economic Growth:** Contributes to economic growth by enabling businesses to operate efficiently and effectively.

Impact of Infrastructure Score Card on the Economy

Infrastructure development plays a crucial role in Nigeria's economic growth, and an infrastructure scorecard can help track progress, identify areas for improvement, and inform investment decisions. Here's how infrastructure impacts Nigeria's economy:

Economic Impacts:

1. **GDP Loss:** Poor road infrastructure results in an annual direct economic impact of about \$7.8 billion, representing 1.6% of Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (World Bank, 2019).
2. **Increased Costs:** Road freight systems experience increased maintenance costs due to poor road conditions, with an estimated annual loss of ₦157 billion from vehicle maintenance on trucks (Federal Ministry of Transportation, 2020).
3. **Travel Time Loss:** Poor road infrastructure leads to significant travel time loss, with an average lead time of 3.5 days (84 hours) for road freight from origin to destination in Nigeria, compared to a calculated standard lead time of 12.46 hours (Nigerian Institute of Transport Technology, 2020).

Benefits of Infrastructure Scorecard:

1. **Improved Planning:** Helps identify areas for improvement and inform investment decisions (Nigerian Society of Engineers, 2020).
2. **Job Creation:** Tracks progress in infrastructure development and its impact on job creation (International Labor Organization, 2019).
3. **Economic Growth:** Contributes to economic growth by enabling businesses to operate efficiently and effectively (World Bank, 2019).

Key Sectors Benefiting from Infrastructure Development:

1. **Transportation:** Roads, rail lines, and public transportation systems create jobs in construction, civil engineering, and transportation services (Federal Ministry of Transportation, 2020).
2. **Renewable Energy:** Renewable energy projects create new job opportunities in installation, maintenance, and manufacturing (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2020).
3. **ICT and Digital Economy:** Investments in digital infrastructure enable remote work, e-commerce, and digital entrepreneurship, creating jobs in the tech sector (Nigerian Communications Commission, 2020).

Figure 4 below shows the general impact of infrastructure score card preparation on the economy.

Source: 2021 infrastructure report card (www.infrastructurereportcard.org)

By investing in infrastructure development, Nigeria can reduce the economic impacts of poor infrastructure and promote sustainable economic growth. The Nigerian Society of Engineers has produced an Infrastructure Ranking Scorecard for Nigeria, highlighting the importance of infrastructure development in infrastructure development (Federal Ministry of Transportation, 2020).

CONCLUSION

Nigeria ranks top in the list of countries with highest unemployment rate globally; World Bank (2021). Infact, unemployment rose from 6.4% in 2010 to 33.3% in 2020. A total of 23.18 million persons in Nigeria either had no jobs or worked less than 20 hours a week, making both categories unemployed. The number of Nigerians of working age but inactive in the labour force increased from 29 million in 2014 to 52 million in 2020. Investment in infrastructure is a sure means to provide jobs and boost Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SME's). Bold leadership and action, sustained investment and focus on resilience are critical requirements to raising the national infrastructure grade.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. To improve the quality of life in Nigeria and strengthen competitiveness, a strategic and holistic plan to review, modernize, and invest in infrastructure are very imperative. Basic maintenance should be a priority so that legacy systems can be improved upon. Policy makers and government must understand that a nation's infrastructure is indeed as strong as its weakest link, just as in all other economic indices.
2. To raise the national infrastructure grade in order for families, communities and businesses to thrive, the three critical requirements of: bold leadership and action, sustained investment, and a focus on resilience are paramount.
3. Leadership and action – investments must be spent wisely, projects must be prioritized especially those with critical benefits to the economy, public safety, environment and quality of life.
4. Sustained investment – increased, long-term and consistent investment is required. Nigeria has to increase her public projects investment to 5% of her GDP as against the previous maximum of 3%. The Public Private Partnerships (PPP) model must be vastly improved to make it very effective.
5. Resilience – new approaches, materials, and technologies must be utilized to ensure the country's infrastructure can speedily recover from both natural and man-made hazards. Green infrastructure should also be adopted.

REFERENCES

- AfDB. (2018). African Economic Outlook 2018.
- African Development Bank (2020). African Economic Outlook 2020.
- Agbigbe, W. (2018). Impact of government infrastructural development on economic growth in Nigeria.
- Akinbogun, S. (2019). Vandalism of infrastructure in Nigeria.
- ASCE (2020). Infrastructure Report Card.
- Calderón, C., & Servén, L. (2004). The effects of infrastructure development on growth and income distribution.
- Calderón, C., & Servén, L. (2004). The effects of infrastructure development on growth and income distribution.
- Cambridge Dictionary (Nd): Institution/En Available from: <https://www.twi-global.com/technical-knowledge/> Accessed: March 13,2023
- Energy Commission of Nigeria (2020). Energy Commission of Nigeria Annual Report 2020.
- EPA (2020). Green Infrastructure.
- FMoT (2020). Federal Ministry of Transportation Annual Report 2020.
- FMWH (2020). Federal Ministry of Works and Housing Annual Report 2020.
- Høyland, B., Moene, K., & Willumsen, F. (2012). The tyranny of international index rankings Journal of Development Economics, 97(1), 1-14.
- International Labor Organization (2019). World Employment Social Outlook 2019.
- International Labor Organization (2020). World Employment Social Outlook 2020.
- International Renewable Energy Agency (2020). Global Renewables Outlook 2020.
- IPCC (2014). Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Vulnerability, and Adaptation.

- IPCC. (2018). Global Warming of 1.5°C.
- IRENA (2019). Global Renewables Outlook: Transforming the Energy System.
- ITU. (2020). World Telecommunication/ICT Development Report 2020.
- Krugman, P. (1994). Competitiveness: A Dangerous Obsession.
- Nigerian Communications Commission (2020). Nigerian Communications Commission Annual Report 2020.
- Nigerian Institute of Transport Technology (2020). Annual Report 2020.
- Nigerian Railway Corporation (2020). Nigerian Railway Corporation Annual Report 2020.
- Nigerian Society of Engineers (2017) Nigerian Infrastructural Report card
- Nigeria's Infrastructure (2022). Midstream and Downstream Gas Infrastructure Fund.
- NSE (2020). Nigerian Society of Engineers Infrastructure Ranking Scorecard.
- Occupational Outlook handbook, OOH (2023): US Bureau of Labor Statistics Available from: www.bls.gov/ohh Accessed: March 13, 2023
- Ogunjumo, A. (2018). Road transport infrastructure development in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
- Statista (2023): Global country ranking by quality of infrastructure 2019 available from: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/264753/ranking-of-countries-according-to-the-general-quality-of-infrastructure/> Accessed: March 13, 2023
- The Nigerian Institution of Civil Engineers (2023) Memorandum and articles of Association (2021); Corporate Affairs Commission, Federal Republic of Nigeria.
- Transparency International (2020). Corruption Perceptions Index 2020.
- UNCTAD (2020). World Investment Report 2020.
- UNESCO (2020). Education for All 2020.
- UN-Habitat (2020). Urban Green Infrastructure.
- UN-Habitat (2020). Urban Planning for Sustainable Development.
- United Nations (2020). Sustainable Development Goals.
- WEF (2020). The Future of Jobs Report 2020.
- World Bank (2019). World Development Report 2019: The Changing Nature of Work.
- World Bank (2020). World Development Report 2020..
- World Economic Forum (2020). The Global Competitiveness Report 2020.
- World Economic Forum (WEF) (2019): Statista: Global Country Ranking by Quality of Infrastructure 2019 Available from: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/264753/ranking-of-.....> Accessed: September 13, 2025
- World Health Organization (2019). World Health Report 2019.
- World Intellectual Property Organization (2020). Global Innovation Index 2020.
- World Trade Organization (2020). World Trade Report 2020.